

STUDIES ON GENETIC VARIABILITY, HERITABILITY AND GENETIC ADVANCE IN GARDEN pea (*Pisum sativum* L.)

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Abstract

The present investigation was carried out at the crop research centre-1, Department of Horticulture, School of Agriculture, ITM University, Gwalior (M.P.). The experimental material comprised of twenty genotypes, which were collected from Indian Institute of Vegetable Research (IIVR), Varanasi which are grown in Gwalior Chambal region which comes under Grid Region of Agro-climatic zone. The experiment was laid out in Randomized Block Design (RBD). Fourteen parameters through genetic variability, heritability and genetic advances for yield and yield attributing Characters were observed and recorded. Results revealed that, the maximum pod yield per plant was recorded in variety NDVP-104, DVP-8 followed by Variety Kashi Ageti, Pusa Pragati and Shihara local. Heritability exerts at high degree for almost all character's studies viz. pod length, shelling percentage, pod weight, pod yield per plot, total number of seeds per pod, days to first flowering, days to first pod set, days to 50% flowering, plant height, average pod diameter and days to first pod picking or harvesting). High estimates of heritability (>95%) were recorded for characters viz. germination % (99.01), pod yield per plot (98.98%), first flower node (98.18%), number of pods per plant (95.76%), number of seeds per plant (95.70 %), pod length (cm) (94.21%), pod weight (94.77%), days to first fruit setting (92.05%), days to first flowering (91.63%) and shelling percentage (91.19%). The estimation of phenotypic coefficient of variance was higher than the genotypic coefficient of variance for all traits.

Keywords: genetic variability, heritability, yield, traits, germination, garden pea

Introduction

A member of Fabaceae family and the famous plant species in which G.H. Mendel worked out Mendel's Law and Genetic principles. Legumes belong to ones of the most important crops worldwide, having major impacts on agriculture, the environment, animal/human nutrition and health (Graham & Vance *et al.*, 2003) Pea is one of the earliest food crops, which thrives well in places with cool climate and is grown in almost all temperate regions of the world.

The garden pea is also known as the common pea and is one of the most important vegetables in the world. It is an annual Herbaceous, self-pollinated legume crop. Peas are starchy but, high in fibre, protein, vitamins (vitamin A, C, K and B complex vitamins such as folic acid, niacin, thiamine and pyridoxine), minerals (iron, magnesium, phosphorus and zinc) and lutein (a yellow carotenoid pigment that benefits vision). The protein of peas contains all the essential amino acids important for the normal activity of living organisms about (27%) for human consumption. Each 100 g edible portion of the green pea contains moisture 78 g, protein 6.3 g, carbohydrates 14.4 g, energy 84 Kcal, calcium 26 mg, phosphorus 116 mg, iron 1.9 mg and vitamin A 640 IU (Thamburaj, 2001) The pea is well placed to meet the increased global demand for high protein human food and animal feed and to act as a leguminous break crop in diverse farming systems (Ambrose *et al.*, 1997). The work examinations were completed to figure out the hereditary variety, interrelationship among various characters and the immediate and roundabout commitment of these characters towards yield.

It is a significant yield with a rich history in hereditary examination tracing all the way back to the old-style work by the father of hereditary qualities (genetics) Gregor J. Mendel. There, should be information on the presence of hereditary changeability, the method of legacy of monetary characters, heritability, the sort of quality activity and the general greatness of added substance, strength and complete genotypic and phenotypic difference of the population.

The correlation studies provide information about association between any two characters. Knowledge of correlation among different traits and further portioning them into direct and indirect effects is one of approaches to understand nature and extent of such relationship. The genotypic correlation indicates the extents to which two characters are under the control of same set of genes having the physiological basis of their expression

Materials And Methods

The present investigation was carried out at the CRC-1, Department of Horticulture, School of Agriculture, ITM University, Gwalior (M.P.). The experimental material comprised of twenty genotypes which were collected from different source and these genotypes are grown in Chambal region of Gwalior which comes under Grid Region

of Agro-climatic zone. The genotypes collected from Indian Institute of Vegetable Research (IIVR) Varanasi are mentioned in the table 1. Phenotypic and genotypic coefficients of variation were estimated by following the procedure given by Burton (1952) heritability in broad sense (h^2) by Burton and De Vane (1953) and genetic advance i.e., the expected genetic gain by using the procedure given by Johnson *et al.*, (1955).

The genotypes were grown in a randomized block design with three replicates in the field size of 40 × 9.5 m during winter season keep row to row distance of 45 cm and plant to plant distance of 20 × 10 cm while seeds are placed about 2.5 cm deep during the year 2022-2023. Data were recorded on five randomly selected competitive plants of each genotype from each replication for fourteen characters viz., days to 50% flowering, node number of first flowering, days to first flowering, number of pods per plant, pod length (cm), plant height at first harvesting (cm), number of pods per plant, pod length (cm), number seeds per pod (g), pod weight (g), pod diameter (mm), days to first fruit setting, shelling percentage (%) and pod yield per plant (g).

Results And Discussion**Analysis of variance:**

Analysis of variance, general mean and range of variation for different characters are given in Table 2 and mean values of all genotypes for all characters are presented in Table 3. The studies indicated that there was a wide range of variability in the germplasm for all the characters under study viz., days to first flowering, days to 50% flowering, days to first pod harvesting, plant height (cm), first flower node, germination (%), days to first fruit setting, number of pods per plant, pod length (cm), pod weight (g), pod diameter, number of seeds per pods, shelling percentage and pod yield per plot For all of the investigated characters, analysis of variance revealed a substantial difference between the accessions. The degree of variation with regard to the range, mean, phenotypic and genotypic coefficients of variation, heritability, and genetic progress are given in Table 3. The current analysis found that all of the analyzed traits varied significantly. Such a vast range of variance demonstrated the potential to increase the population of these traits. Numerous characters showed high coefficients of phenotypic (PCV) and genotypic (GCV) variance, the highest being for leaf area followed by fruit length, total fruit yield per plant, leaf chlorophyll and no. of fruit per plant. The high PCV and GCV observed are a result of their great variability, which in turn provides favourable selection opportunities. The lowest PCV and GCV were for pod yield per plot, germination % and pod weight.

High heritability alone does not enough to make effective selection in advance generations unless accompanied by substantial amount of

genetic advance Gupta *et al.*, (2006) and Katoch *et al.*, (2016). A high estimate of heritability along with high genetic advance provides good scope for further improvement in advance generations. Thus, the degree of success in selection depends upon the magnitude of heritability as well as genetic advance. In the present investigation, heritability values were ranged from 82.28% (days to first pod harvesting) to 99.28% (pod weight). The highest heritability was recorded for pod weight followed by germination %, pod yield; first flower node appears and number of seeds per pod. Pal and Singh (2013), Kumar *et al.* (2013), Kumar *et al.*, (2004), found high heritability estimates for days to 50% flowering, plant height and number of pods per plant respectively. The medium heritability was recorded in number of pods per plant and pod length. The lowest heritability was noted for days to first pod harvesting, days to 50% flowering followed by shelling percentage and days to first flowering. The value of expected genetic advance in per cent of mean was highest for pod yield and germination %. The lowest value of genetic advance was recorded for shelling percentage and days to 50% flowering.

Coefficient of variability:

For 20 characteristics, estimates of the phenotypic and genotypic coefficients of variability are shown in Table 3. In general, for all 20 characteristics, the magnitude of phenotypic coefficient of variability was greater than genetic coefficient of variability. We found a wide range of phenotypic and genotypic coefficients of variation. The highest phenotypic as well as genotypic coefficients of variation were observed in case of pod yield per plot (50.29% and 50.03%), germination % (45.52% and 45.25%), pod weight (43.41% and 43.25%) and number of seeds per pod (18.34% and 17.95%). However, the difference between the PCV and GCV was paltry, which is indicating the high contribution of genetic components in phenotypic expression of these characters. The moderate PCV% as well as GCV% were observed first flower node (28.92 and 28.66) followed by number of seeds per pods (18.34 and 17.95), number of pods per plant (17.66 and 17.28), pod length (16.09 and 15.62), days to first flowering (13.82 and 13.23) and shelling percentage (13.16 and 12.57). The phenotypic and genotypic coefficients of variations were lower for days to first fruit setting (13.74 and 13.18), days to 50% flowering (11.56 and 10.91) and days to first pod harvesting (9.82 and 8.91) low GCV and PCV for these traits indicated that there was less variation for these traits.

Heritability and genetic advance

Heritability in broad sense of a character is important to the breeder. It indicates the possibility and extent to improvement is possible through selection. High heritability alone does not enough to make effective selection in advance generations unless accompanied by substantial amount of genetic advance Gupta *et al.*, (2006), and Katoch *et al.*, (2016). A high estimate of heritability along with high genetic advance provides good scope for further improvement in advance generations. Thus, the degree of success in selection depends upon the magnitude of heritability as well as genetic advance. In the present investigation, heritability values were ranged from 82.28% (days to first pod harvesting) to 99.28% (pod weight). The highest heritability was recorded for pod weight followed by germination %, pod yield, first flower node appears and number of seeds per pod. Pal and Singh (2013), Kumar *et al.*, (2013), Kumar *et al.*, (2004), found high heritability estimates for days to 50% flowering, plant height and number of pods per plant respectively. The medium heritability was recorded in number of pods per plant and pod length. The lowest heritability was noted for days to first pod harvesting, days to 50% flowering followed by shelling percentage and days to first flowering. The value of expected genetic advance in per cent of mean was highest for pod yield and germination %. The lowest value of genetic advance was recorded for shelling percentage and days to 50% flowering. Rajbhar *et al.*, (2017) estimated high genetic advance in per cent of mean for number of pods per plant, primary branches per plant and pod yield per plant in support of above finding. The

magnitude of high heritability coupled with high genetic advance were recorded for pod yield, germination % and pod weight. Gupta *et al.*, (2006) also reported high heritability coupled with high genetic advance was observed for days to first flowering nodes, plant height, number of first flowering nodes, dry matter weight per plant, green pod yield per plant and number of primary branches per plant indicated that selection for these traits should be effective for improving economic yield.

Genetic advance in per cent of mean:

The maximum contribution in manifestation of total genetic divergence was made by days to first flowering (10.76 %) followed by days to first pod harvesting (10.45 %). The minimum contribution was noticed in case of pod yield per plot (kg) (2.23%) and shelling percentage (2.26 %) toward genetic divergence. The role of days pod weight (5.19%), number of seeds per pods (5.28%), germination (%) (5.64 %) and first flower node appearance (7.18%) were very low in manifestation of total genetic divergence in the available germplasm.

Highest per cent contribution towards clustering of genotypes were observed in days to first flowering (10.76%), days to first pod harvesting (10.45 %), plant height (9.55 %), number of pods per plant (8.79 %), days to first fruit setting (8.36 %), pod diameter (8.10 %), pod length (7.45 %), first flower node (7.18 %), germination % (5.64 %), number of seeds per plant (5.28 %). The overall review of the results obtained by genetic diversity study in present investigation revealed that the crosses between the entries separated by the large inter-cluster distance and having high cluster mean values for one or other character will be helpful in the improvement of this important crop i.e., garden pea

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Conclusion

Based on mean performance only one genotype *Kashi Ageti* in early group and seven genotypes *viz.* NDVP-104, *Pusa Pragati*, DVP-8, *Shihara local*, *Kashi Shakti*, VRPD-1, *Azad Pea-1* in mid-season group were found as significant and most promising genotypes for pod yield per plant along with some other traits. The estimates of phenotypic coefficients of variation (PCV) were higher than genotypic coefficients of variation (GCV) for all the traits. High magnitude of variability was observed in case of pods yield per plot (50.29%), Germination % (45.52), pod weight (43.41%), first flower node appearance (28.92%), number of seeds per pod (18.34%) and number of pods per plant (17.66%). High heritability coupled with high genetic advance in per cent of mean were observed for pod yield per plot, germination %, pod weight, first flower node appearance, number of seeds per pod and number of pods per plant indicating scope of high selection response. Path coefficient analysis revealed that number of seeds per pod followed by number of pods per plant and pod length exhibited considerable positive direct effect on yield, while negative direct contribution towards yield were pronounced by plant height, shelling percentage and days to first pod harvesting both at phenotypic and genotypic levels.

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Table 1: Details of garden pea genotypes used in the experiment

S. No.	Genotypes	Source
1	KashiNandini	IIVR, Varanasi
2	Kashishakti	IIVR, Varanasi
3	KashiMukti	IIVR, Varanasi
4	Kashi Samarth	IIVR, Varanasi
5	ArkaAjeet	IIVR, Varanasi
6	ArkaUttam	IIVR, Varanasi
7	KashiSamrddhi	IIVR, Varanasi
8	ArkaPriya	IIVR, Varanasi
9	PusaPragati	IIVR, Varanasi
10	NDVP-104	IIVR, Varanasi
11	DVP-8	IIVR, Varanasi
12	PB-89	IIVR, Varanasi
13	Snow pea	IIVR, Varanasi
14	Shihara local	IIVR, Varanasi
15	Mithiphalli	IIVR, Varanasi
16	Azad pea-1	IIVR, Varanasi
17	VRPD-1	IIVR, Varanasi
18	CHP-2	IIVR, Varanasi
19	VL-3	IIVR, Varanasi
20	KashiAgeti	IIVR, Varanasi

Table 2: Analysis of variance (mean squares) for fourteen quantitative characters in garden pea.

S.No.	Traits	Sources of Variation		
		Replication	Treatment	Error
	DF	2	19	38
1.	Days to first flowering	4.7	162.5**	4.80
2.	Days to 50% flowering	0.04	166.35**	6.58
3.	Days to first pod Harvesting	7.1	122.36**	8.20
4.	Plant Height	0.07	198.4**	6.61
5.	First Flower Node	0.18	27.07**	0.17
6.	Germination (%)	2.43	1646.95**	5.47
7.	Days to First Fruit setting	2.58	286.16**	8.00
8.	Number of Pods per plant	0.8	28.71**	0.42
9.	Pod length (cm)	0.06	3.764**	0.08
10.	Pod Weight (gm)	0.07	9.58**	0.02
11.	Pod Diameter	0.209	5.135**	0.09
12.	Number of seeds per Pods	0.035	3.286**	0.05
13.	Shelling Percentage	1.6	124.38**	3.88
14.	Pod yield per plot (kg)	0.073	0.307**	0.00

***, significant at 5% and 1% level, respectively

Table 3: Genetic variability, estimates of range, grand mean, phenotypic (PCV) and genotypic (GCV) coefficient of variation, heritability in broad sense, genetic advance (Ga) and genetic advance in per cent of mean for fourteen characters in garden pea.

Genotypes	Mean	Min.	Max.	var. (g)	var. (p)	Heritability (%)	GA	GA% mean	GCV (%)	PCV (%)	% cont.
Days to first flowering	54.80	33.33	65.33	52.57	57.37	91.63	14.30	26.09	13.23	13.82	10.76
Days to 50% flowering	66.92	44.67	78.00	53.26	59.84	89.00	14.18	21.19	10.91	11.56	8.76
Days to first pod Harvesting	74.13	54.33	85.00	38.06	46.25	82.28	11.53	16.65	8.91	9.82	10.45
Plant Height	65.58	46.53	75.13	63.93	70.54	90.62	15.68	23.91	12.19	12.81	9.55
First Flower Node	10.45	6.00	17.00	8.97	9.13	98.18	6.11	58.49	28.66	28.92	7.18
Germination (%)	51.64	3.45	85.72	547.16	552.63	99.01	47.95	92.84	45.29	45.52	5.64
Days to First Fruit setting	67.33	44.67	72.67	92.72	100.72	92.05	19.03	26.06	13.18	13.74	8.36
Number of Pods per plant	17.77	10.99	23.68	9.43	9.85	95.76	6.19	34.84	17.28	17.66	8.79
Pod length(cm)	7.10	4.63	9.67	1.23	1.31	94.21	2.22	31.23	15.62	16.09	7.45
Pod Weight(gm)	4.13	1.55	7.83	3.18	3.21	99.25	3.66	88.75	43.25	43.41	5.19
Pod Diameter	7.58	5.23	10.42	1.68	1.77	94.77	2.60	34.32	17.11	17.58	8.10
Number of seeds per Pods	5.79	4.37	7.77	1.08	1.13	95.70	2.09	36.17	17.95	18.34	5.28
Shelling Percentage	50.42	36.28	64.17	40.17	44.05	91.19	12.47	24.73	12.57	13.16	2.26
Pod yield per plot (kg)	0.64	0.17	1.25	0.10	0.10	98.98	0.65	102.54	50.03	50.29	2.23

Min.: Minimum, **Max.:** Maximum, **var. (g):** Variability (Genotypic), **var. (p):** Variability (Phenotypic), **GA:** Genetic advance, **GCV:** Genotypic coefficient of variation, **PCV:** Phenotypic coefficient of variation and **% cont.:** Per cent contribution